

Eveline Wandl-Vogt (1), Barbara Piringner (1), Yalemisew Abgaz (2),
Katalin Lejtovicz (1), Amelie Dorn (1)

Making the invisible visible: exploring and exploiting person information as an access layer to heterogeneous data facilitating inclusive, gender-symmetric research

- (1) Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (AT)
- (2) Dublin City University, Adapt Centre (IE)

How our world is organised differently by men and women and represented in German language has been widely studied (cf. Pober et al., 2016; Pusch 1991). In this paper, we offer a cross-disciplinary view on biographical and prosopographical data, serving as an access layer for diverse data collections, demonstrated on the example of the DH-project exploreAT! (2015-2019) (cf. Wandl-Vogt et al, 2015) with the aim to enable inclusive, gender-symmetric and cross-data-set approaches within (humanities) research. The collection exploreAT! draws on (~ 5 mio. paper slips), was compiled by ~11.100 persons of various professional backgrounds and different roles in the curation and compilation process of almost a century. As an early humanities crowdsourced project, exploreAT! deals with ordinary people and people of regional importance. Thus, knowledge about persons involved in the data collection is key for judging data quality and deriving knowledge. Since the beginning of the project (early 20th century), the data have been documented in the institute's archive, and since the late 1990s a "Mitarbeiterdatenbank" (employee database) provides access to documentation of persons in a structured way. To-date, these data are modelled, published and stored in a MySQL-database, cross-referenced with geo-referenced biographical and bibliographical information and interlinked with their collections. Here, we exemplify how these person information can be used as a central access point to heterogeneous (research) data, important for tracking project related quality information. We introduce an enriched data model, based on work from the APIS project, mapped with the experiences, learnings and needs from exploreAT!, aiming to make unknown persons re-searchable and visible, while contributing to more inclusive acknowledgements.

DATENBANK DER
BAIRISCHEN MUNDARTEN
IN ÖSTERREICH @ ELECTRONICALLY MAPPED

Abfrage Projekt Ressourcen

Index

Index

- Lemma
- Bibliographie
- Personen
- Orte
- Gemeinden
- Regionen
- Fragebuch

Personen und Institutionen

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z

< Zurück 1 2 3 4 5 ... 9 Weiter >

Bauer, Werner

Baumgartner, Johann

Baumgartner, Johann

Bayer, Käthe

<https://wboe.oeaw.ac.at/dboe/indices/person/indexengine.pager.actionlink/W/1?ac=B/3>

<https://wboe.oeaw.ac.at/dboe/indices/person/B/3>

DATENBANK DER
BAIRISCHEN MUNDARTEN
IN ÖSTERREICH @ ELECTRONICALLY MAPPED

Abfrage Projekt Ressourcen

Index

Index

- Lemma
- Bibliographie
- Personen
- Orte
- Gemeinden
- Regionen
- Fragebuch

Person

Werner Bauer

Allgemeines

- * 1939, Zederthls.
- Herausgeber
- Autor
- Sammler

Quellen

1 2 3 4 5 ... 11 Weiter >

- Aufn.Brambg.-W.(1970a)
- Aufn.Brambg.-W.(1970b)
- Aufn.Brambg.-W.(1970c)
- Aufn.Brambg.-W.(1970d)
- Aufn.Brixen/T.(1974-1975)
- Aufn.Donau Schwaben.(1978)
- Aufn.Eisenratten.(1978)
- Aufn.Fieberbr.(1974-1975a)

<https://wboe.oeaw.ac.at/dboe/person/22192>

<https://wboe.oew.ac.at/dboe/person/22192>

References

APIS - Mapping historical networks: Building the new Austrian Prosopographical | Biographical Information System (APIS) <https://www.oew.ac.at/en/acdh/projects/apis/> project website: <https://apis.acdh.oew.ac.at/> [access: 03.10.2017]

exploreAT! - exploring austria's culture through the language glass. project website: <https://exploreat.usal.es/> [access: 03.10.2017]

Pober, M., Geyer, I., Wandl-Vogt, E. & Piringer, B. (2016) Von vielrednerischen Weibern und alles erforschenden Männern – Genderasymmetrien in der Datenbank der bairischen Mundarten in Österreich (DBÖ) im Vergleich mit Großwörterbüchern der Gegenwart. Tinatin Margalitadze and Meladze, George. Proceedings of the XVII EURALEX International Congress. Lexicography and Linguistic Diversity. 6 – 10 September, 2016. Tbilisi. online: <https://euralex.org/publications/von-vielrednerischen-weibern-und-alles-erforschenden-mannern-genderasymmetrien-in-der-datenbank-der-bairischen-mundarten-in-osterreich-dbo-im-vergleich-mit-grosworderbuchern-der-gegenwart/> [access: 03.10.2017]

Pusch, L. F. (1991). Das Deutsche als Männersprache. Aufsätze und Glossen zur feministischen Linguistik. 1. Aufl. Frankfurt/M.: Suhrkamp.

Wandl-Vogt, E. (2010) Datenbank der bairischen Mundarten in Österreich electronically mapped (dbo@ema) II.Teil I: Pilze. <https://wboe.oeaw.ac.at/> [access: 03.10.2017]

Wandl-Vogt, E., O'Connor, A., Theron, R. & Kieslinger, B. (2015) exploreAT! Re-thinking lexicography. AELINCO 2015. Book of Abstracts. 7th Conference on Corpus Linguistics, Valladolid (Spain), 5-7 March 2015.